

Automated segmentation of peripheral arteries in 3D CT data based on a Single-Depth vascular network

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ABSTRACT

Peripheral artery disease (PAD), if left untreated, can lead to cardiovascular mortality. The diagnosis of PAD typically requires complex and costly procedures, such as computed tomography (CT), followed by extensive examinations. In addition, segmenting peripheral arteries through deep networks still remains challenging due to their small and complex structure, motion artifacts, class imbalance, and variations in field of view in different datasets. Furthermore, handling large-scale whole-body scans efficiently complicates the segmentation process. To address these limitations, this study employs three-dimensional CT scans to segment peripheral arteries. Firstly, a YOLOv8 network is developed to extract the region of interest (ROI) from whole-body scans. This approach optimizes processing by focusing on ROI while reducing memory usage and processing time. Afterwards, ROI is fed into a novel Single-Depth Vascular Network for peripheral artery segmentation. The Single-Depth Vascular Network encapsulates an encoder–decoder architecture with a skip connection to improve the accuracy and precision of segmentation. Through this approach, the network achieves an average Dice similarity coefficient of 0.91, a Hausdorff distance of 12.60 mm, and a 95th percentile Hausdorff distance of 1.12 mm against unseen data. This approach provides a tool for medical professionals to diagnose and treat PAD with greater precision.

1. Introduction

Peripheral arterial disease (PAD) is a prevalent circulatory condition characterized by narrowed or blocked arteries, leading to reduced blood flow to the limbs and potentially serious complications [1]. Common symptoms of PAD include discomfort, spasms, and, in severe instances, tissue damage or gangrene [2]. In extreme cases, PAD can result in cardiac death [3]. Recently, there is a rise in PAD cases, closely linked to cardiovascular diseases that contribute to increased mortality and morbidity [4].

In the human body, the aorta serves as the largest artery [5], supplying oxygenated blood as the primary route to systemic circulation. It consists of three main sections: the ascending aorta, the aortic arch, and the descending aorta, which further branches into the common iliac arteries [5,6]. These iliac arteries continue into the femoral arteries, which, along with their branches, form the peripheral arterial system [7]. These peripheral arteries (PAs) are crucial for delivering oxygenated blood to the lower limbs, thereby ensuring their health.

1.1. Imaging techniques for diagnosing PAD

The diagnosis of the PAD can be time-consuming and a complex process. Identifying PAs through medical imaging techniques is the initial step.

Commonly utilized imaging methods encompass computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance angiography (MRA), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and ultrasonography (USG). CT scans are one of the most commonly used imaging techniques for the examination of PAs. Since MRA has a higher sensitivity to motion, which affects the image quality, especially for smaller blood vessels [8]. A CT scanner employs a contrast agent to generate images of blood vessels. This technique effectively displays the arterial system, including the abdomen, pelvis, and lower extremities [9]. CT scans produce high-quality images that help doctors see the arteries in detail. In addition, CT scans can provide a complete evaluation of the arterial system in one scan, making them an important tool for the diagnosis of PAD [10].

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The interpretation of medical images is subjective, leading to diagnostic variability among practitioners. Healthcare professionals face multiple challenges when analyzing medical images, making the task both complex and demanding [8]. These variations may lead to incorrect diagnoses or postponements in treatment, adversely affecting patient outcomes. In addition, the complexity of medical images is increased by issues such as noise, low resolution, and artifacts, which obstruct accurate analysis. The large volume of medical images also adds to the workload, which requires significant time and effort from medical experts (e.g. CT data with a resolution of $512 \times 512 \times 2311$). These challenges underscore the need for automated systems to support practitioners, ensuring more consistent, accurate, and efficient analysis [11].

1.2. Literature review on artery segmentation techniques

The literature has proposed multiple approaches to identify and segment arteries from the rest of the body, considering their structure and nature. Early methods for artery segmentation relied heavily on edge detection and region-growing algorithms. These methods often struggled with the noise and artifacts present in medical images [12]. Techniques such as active contour models (snakes) and level-set methods have been used to improve segmentation accuracy. These methods use prior knowledge about the shape and appearance of the arteries to guide the segmentation process [8]. Recent advances in machine learning, particularly deep learning, have significantly improved segmentation performance. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and U-Net architectures are among the applications. These models can learn complex features from large datasets, making them highly effective for medical image segmentation [13]. Combining traditional image processing with machine learning techniques has also shown promise. These hybrid methods leverage the strengths of both approaches to achieve better segmentation results [14]. Flores et al. presented the use of machine learning and AI in the detection of advanced and undiagnosed PAD, the refinement of disease characterization, the personalization of medical decision-making, the improvement of risk stratification, the automaton of image analysis and the direction of vascular surgical care [15].

Dima et al. presented a novel method for segmenting 3D pancreatic arteries from single annotated 2D projections with depth supervision, demonstrating effective capture of depth information from 2D projections [16]. Guo et al. addressed the challenge of annotating vessels in 3D space by using maximum intensity projection (MIP) to reduce the dimensionality of 3D volumes to 2D images for efficient annotation. The 2D labels guide the training of a 3D vessel segmentation model, which is further refined using confidence learning and uncertainty estimation [17]. In contrast, Chen et al. proposed a novel 3D shape-guided local discrimination model for 3D vascular segmentation, leveraging limited guidance from public 2D vessel annotations. The model uses a 3D region discrimination loss to learn voxel-wise similarities and a Crop-and-Overlap strategy to generate reference masks from 2D annotations [18]. However, in case of segmentation of PAs, Hu et al. presented the association between the lower extremity muscle characteristics of CTA and the severity of PAD using digital subtraction angiography (DSA) as a reference standard [19]. In addition, Westenberg et al. focused on developing and validating methods for accurately measuring vessel diameters, crucial for diagnosing and treating PAD using gadolinium contrast-enhanced three-dimensional MRA [20]. Despite these advancements, there is still no dedicated solution for CT-based segmentation of PAs.

1.3. Computational challenges and class imbalance in artery segmentation

The intricate branching structures and varied diameters of the PAs require models to account for high variability in arterial morphology, particularly in regions with bifurcations and overlapping vessels,

which can confuse segmentation algorithms [21]. Furthermore, in CT scans, PAs often appear with low contrast against surrounding tissues such as muscles and bones, making it difficult to clearly distinguish arterial boundaries. Image artifacts caused by patient motion, metal implants, or limitations of the scanner further obscure PAs, complicating segmentation efforts.

Identification of smaller vessels in the legs represents specific challenges. These arteries are thin and often consist of few pixels with scan, leading to difficult detection and segmentation. In case of lower image resolution, this task becomes more complicated [22]. The use of deep neural networks for large amounts of 3D medical imaging datasets requires substantial memory and processing resources. Accurate segmentation on these volumes in a reasonable time span requires significant computational resources and effective algorithms to prevent bottlenecks [23].

Class imbalance is another challenge, as the arteries occupy a relatively small portion of the image volume compared to surrounding tissues, such as muscles or bones. In addition, patient-specific factors such as age, body habit, and the presence of comorbidities (e.g., diabetes, obesity) influence the appearance of the arteries on scans, complicating the development of generalized models that can accurately segment PAs in a diverse population of patients [24].

In addition, indicating the region of interest (ROI) in medical imaging is challenging because scans often include structures that do not contain PAs, making it harder to isolate and accurately segment relevant regions. Non-relevant structures such as the lungs, heart, and major thoracic vessels (e.g. the aorta, subclavian, and carotid arteries) can dominate the scan, leading to the unnecessary inclusion of non-target anatomy. Moreover, medical imaging often captures a wide field of view, and precisely segmenting the relevant region while excluding the upper body without losing crucial lower-body information requires accurate localization.

To address these challenges, an advanced methodology for detecting ROI and a model for segmenting PAs is necessary.

1.4. A novel approach to PAs segmentation using YOLOv8 and Single-Depth Vascular Network

This study presents a novel approach that integrates advanced techniques to improve the precision and efficiency of PAs segmentation. This work presents a You-Only-Look-Once version 8 (YOLOv8) based method for ROI extraction integrated with cumulative intensity projection (CIP). This integration significantly detects key regions on CT scan. In addition, the study develops and presents a novel Single-Depth vascular network (SDVN) for PA segmentation considering the limitations. SDVN consists of a single encoder–decoder and skip connection to optimize the segmentation process. The SDVN captures more contextual information while maintaining computational efficiency. The simplicity of the single encoder–decoder structure reduces complexity while still providing robust performance in segmenting PAs.

This approach advances medical image segmentation by integrating the advanced ROI detection capabilities of YOLOv8 with the SDVN architecture. This integration improves segmentation accuracy and efficiency, which are essential for the diagnosis and evaluation of PAD.

2. Method

This section encapsulates the proposed methodology in detail, as shown in Fig. 1. Through dataset acquisition and preparation, that is, conversion from anisotropic to isotropic resolution, ROI detection using YOLOv8 for arterial bifurcation points, grid samplers, SDVN, loss function, grid aggregator, and postprocessing are detailed.

Fig. 1. Flowchart outlining the study pipeline for PAs segmentation. The pipeline integrates 3D CT scan data, where YOLOv8 is used for precise ROI detection, specifically identifying key vascular features.

The segmented ROIs are then processed by the SDVN model, enabling efficient and accurate PAs segmentation.

Table 1

Summary of CT scan specifications across models, including resolution, axial views, spacing, and number of cases.

CT Scan Specification	KiTS	RIDER	Dongyang	Gennimatas_1	Gennimatas_2
Resolution (X, Y)	512, 512	512, 512	512, 666	512, 512	512, 512
Axial Slices(Min/Avg/Max)	94/146/1059	260/1008/1140	122/149/251	91/769/2311	91/292/906
Spacing (x, y)[Min, Max](mm)	[0.44, 0.98]	[0.69, 1.37]	[0.54, 0.75]	[0.84, 0.98]	[0.71, 0.98]
Spacing (z) [Min, Max](mm)	[0.50, 5.00]	[0.62, 2.50]	[2.50, 3.03]	[0.63, 3.75]	[0.60, 5.00]
Number of Cases	20	18	18	17	19
Contrast-to-Noise Ratio	0.99 ± 0.53	0.89 ± 0.38	1.05 ± 0.44	1.93 ± 0.83	2.41 ± 0.74
Signal-to-Noise Ratio	1.61 ± 4.18	3.33 ± 1.88	3.50 ± 0.98	3.52 ± 1.53	3.26 ± 0.85
PAs Number of Slices (1mm interval)(Min/Avg/Max)	180/228/301	180/245/283	180/185/237	253/346/848	346/700/786
PAs Region	Common iliac, Internal iliac, External iliac, Deep femoral	Common iliac, Internal iliac, External iliac, Deep femoral	Common iliac, Internal iliac, External iliac, Deep femoral	Common iliac, Internal iliac, External iliac, Common femoral, Popliteal, Anterior tibial, Posterior tibial	Common iliac, Internal iliac, External iliac, Common femoral, Popliteal

2.1. Dataset

For PAs segmentation, CT scans from five separate datasets were used, with each dataset providing unique properties that improve the model's capacity to handle diverse imaging settings and adapt to various real-world scenarios. The dataset consists of CT scans from the KiTS19 Grand Challenge [25], RIDER Lung CT dataset [25], and Dongyang Hospital dataset [25]. All of these datasets are licensed under the CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 license and an end-user license agreement (EULA) In addition to that, two Gennimatas Hospital datasets, one covering the entire body and the other focusing on the torso, created a comprehensive data set crucial for research due to its data variability. The Gennimatas dataset for this study was obtained specifically from Gennimatas Hospital, Athens, Greece. Ethical approval has been granted for the use of this dataset in the study (approvals 9876/28.3.24 and 11293/9.4.24). Patients were selected solely based on a confirmed diagnosis of PAD, without any additional inclusion or exclusion criteria. This approach ensured diagnostic consistency while preserving cohort heterogeneity. The Gennimatas_1 dataset includes 17 patients (13 males and 4 females) aged between 38 and 77 years, with a mean age of 59.1 ± 11.6 years. The Gennimatas_2 dataset consists of 19 patients (11 males and 8 females) aged between 17 and 91 years, with a mean age of 60.2 ± 20.3 years. All CT scans of both datasets were acquired using a GE Revolution EVO scanner.

Fig. 2 illustrates the five different datasets, showing the variations in Field of View (FOV) and other imaging characteristics across the datasets. **Fig. 2** provides a visual representation of the datasets used in the study, allowing a comparison of their structural differences. **Table 1** presents a detailed comparative analysis of the specific characteristics of each dataset, including key attributes such as resolution, axial slices, spacing, and number of cases. **Table 1** also highlights the differences in CT scan specifications across the datasets, which are crucial for understanding the diversity and challenges associated with medical image segmentation.

2.2. Conversion from anisotropic to isotropic resolution

This step involves resampling the CT scans to ensure that the voxel dimensions are the same in all directions. If the original dimensions of the voxel are (dx, dy, dz) , the new isotropic voxel dimensions are set to $(1.0, 1.0, 1.0)$ mm and the image is resampled accordingly [26] as:

$$S_x = \frac{d_x}{d_{iso}}, \quad S_y = \frac{d_y}{d_{iso}}, \quad S_z = \frac{d_z}{d_{iso}} \quad (1)$$

The new dimensions after resampling are:

$$n'_x = \lfloor n_x \cdot S_x \rfloor, \quad n'_y = \lfloor n_y \cdot S_y \rfloor, \quad n'_z = \lfloor n_z \cdot S_z \rfloor \quad (2)$$

where:

Fig. 2. Illustration of variations in the Field of View, size, and spacing across five CT scans from different medical centers. The figure highlights differences in anatomical coverage and imaging parameters between scans.

- d_x, d_y, d_z are the voxel spacings of the anisotropic volume,
- n_x, n_y, n_z are the original dimensions of the anisotropic volume,
- d_{iso} is the target isotropic spacing,
- S_x, S_y, S_z are the scaling factors for the x , y , and z dimensions respectively,
- n'_x, n'_y, n'_z are the new dimensions of the isotropic volume.

2.3. Region of interest detection using YOLOv8 for arterial bifurcation points

The dataset consists of multiple samples, each containing regions of the body not related to PAs. Including these additional regions in the training data can lead to class imbalance, which complicates the training process. This imbalance may reduce the model's performance by causing it to focus on irrelevant body parts, which affects its ability to effectively segment the PAs. To address this issue, an automated method using You Only Look Once version 8 (YOLOv8) is proposed to accurately identify ROI, specifically the PAs structure, which helps to reduce this imbalance. YOLOv8 [27], developed by Ultralytics, is designed for real-time object detection, image classification, instance segmentation, and pose estimation. YOLOv8 was chosen for the extraction of the ROI due to its integrated pose estimation and keypoint detection capabilities, which offer more precise anatomical localization compared to traditional object detection methods that rely solely on bounding boxes. This advanced functionality is crucial for accurately identifying specific anatomical landmarks, thereby streamlining and improving the ROI extraction process. In particular, the YOLOv8 pose estimation feature significantly improves PAs detection and analysis on CT by identifying key points that correspond to critical anatomical structures. By providing both keypoints and bounding boxes, YOLOv8 enables highly accurate localization within the ROI — an essential advantage in medical imaging, where precise spatial relationships between anatomical features are vital. Moreover, benchmarking studies, such as Jegham et al. [28], have shown that YOLOv8 outperforms the available YOLO versions by delivering superior inference speed

while maintaining competitive precision, in complex datasets. This combination of speed, accuracy, and built-in keypoint detection makes YOLOv8 particularly well suited for medical imaging workflows.

In this study, YOLOv8 identifies key points, particularly points of bifurcation of the arteries. By accurately marking these keypoints, the model focuses on essential aspects of arterial anatomy, improving its ability to learn and generalize from the data. This targeted approach improves overall performance, allowing the model to focus on the most informative examples and minimize the influence of irrelevant data that could weaken its training efficacy. The YOLOv8-based pipeline for detecting bifurcation keypoints and their corresponding bounding boxes from 2D projections of 3D CT volumes is illustrated in Fig. 4. This precise localization of vascular features supports downstream segmentation tasks.

2.4. Grid samplers

After the detection of ROI, grid samplers were utilized to improve the model training process.

Grid samplers are used to extract patches from extensive volumetric data, thereby substantially decreasing computational expenses. Furthermore, grid samplers play a vital role in choosing a representative subset of spatial data points, ensuring that the model is trained on a variety of important features [29].

2.5. Single-Depth Vascular Network

The Single-Depth Vascular Network (SDVN) is a convolutional neural network, precisely developed for the segmentation of PAs from three-dimensional volumetric imaging data. The SDVN architecture is designed to preserve high spatial resolution across the processing pipeline, starting with a primary convolutional layer that emphasizes the extraction of essential features from the input data. This preliminary phase is crucial to the network's effectiveness, as it lays the groundwork for a more accurate and streamlined encoding procedure. The following key features highlight the SDVN architecture:

Fig. 3. The SDVN Architecture: Diagram illustrates the interaction between the different components of the network, highlighting its structural flow and functional integration.

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the YOLOv8-based pipeline for PAs analysis. The model detects bifurcation keypoints and their corresponding bounding boxes from 2D projections of 3D CT scan volumes. This enables precise localization of vascular features and supports downstream segmentation tasks.

- SDVN employs a single encoder–decoder pathway with one skip connection, significantly reducing architectural complexity compared to traditional multi-depth or multi-branch networks.
- Prior to each downsampling step, the network utilizes a residual convolutional block that preserves critical spatial information and enhances feature representation stability, ensuring essential details are maintained despite the reduction in spatial resolution.
- This streamlined design reduces the number of trainable parameters, enabling faster training and inference.
- The single skip connection — from the highest encoder level to the decoder — effectively preserves high-resolution spatial details, ensuring precise and detailed vessel segmentation.

Moreover, SDVN addresses sensitivity to small sensor variations and noise through its targeted skip connection and residual convolutional block. These components preserve high-resolution spatial details and critical features early in the network pipeline, enhancing robustness against minor variations and noise in imaging data. A schematic of the SDVN architecture is shown in Fig. 3, which illustrates the interaction between the different components of the network, highlighting its structural flow and functional integration.

The encoder is built with multiple convolutional layers using (3×3×3) kernels and operates with a stride of 2, which not only extracts intricate patterns but also reduces the spatial dimensions of the input data. To introduce controlled non-linearity and prevent the issue of dead neurons, Leaky ReLU (LReLU) activations follow each convolutional layer. As the encoder processes the data, it uses these down-sampling

layers (with a stride of 2) to progressively build deeper and more abstract feature representations.

The transition between the encoder and decoder is facilitated by bridge layers, which act as intermediaries that effectively transfer and prepare the high-dimensional features from the encoder for the decoder. These bridge layers ensure that feature maps retain crucial information needed for accurate spatial reconstruction in the later stages.

A critical component of the SDVN is the single skip connection. This skip connection transfers information specifically from the highest feature level of the encoder directly to the corresponding layer in the decoder. This allows the decoder to access essential high-resolution features that are necessary for detailed and precise segmentation of the PAs. By leveraging this single skip connection, the network ensures that critical spatial details are integrated without over-complicating the architecture.

The decoder restores the spatial dimensions of the feature maps, ensuring that the final segmentation map aligns with the resolution of the original input image, which is essential for accurately reconstructing the detailed structures of the PAs. To optimize network performance, group normalization is applied throughout, normalizing the inputs at each layer to accelerate training and improve overall efficiency.

In summary, the SDVN architecture features a single encoder and decoder connected via strategic bridge layers and a single, precisely positioned skip connection. Using down-sampling and up-sampling layers with strides of 2, the network effectively balances precision. This streamlined design minimizes computational complexity, making it a suitable solution for clinical applications that require advanced image analysis techniques.

2.6. Loss-function

This study uses a loss function that integrates various elements to improve segmentation accuracy, `avg_loss`. The `avg_loss` function includes three main loss terms: Binary Cross Entropy (BCE), soft Dice loss, and soft `clDice` loss. Each component serves a distinct purpose in improving segmentation precision, especially for tubular structures such as the PAs.

2.6.1. Binary cross-entropy loss

The BCE loss is frequently employed in binary classification tasks at the pixel level to measure the deviation between the predicted probability and the ground truth for each pixel [30]. The BCE loss is defined as:

$$\text{BCE} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \log(p_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - p_i)] \quad (3)$$

where y_i is the ground truth label, p_i is the predicted probability, and N is the number of pixels.

Although BCE effectively ensures class distinction, it falls short in accounting for spatial coherence and structural preservation. Therefore, additional loss functions are often incorporated to mitigate these limitations [31].

2.6.2. Soft Dice Loss

Soft Dice Loss aims to enhance the alignment between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth. It is designed to address class imbalance and improve volumetric overlap. The `Dice_loss` is defined as:

$$\text{Dice_loss} = 1 - \frac{2 \sum_{i=1}^N p_i y_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N p_i + \sum_{i=1}^N y_i} \quad (4)$$

where p_i is the predicted probability and y_i is the ground truth label.

This loss function is effective in improving segmentation in medical imaging by ensuring that predicted and actual volumes are closely aligned [32].

2.6.3. Soft `clDice` loss

The `clDice` loss [33] includes topological information to improve the traditional `clDice` loss. Assesses where the morphological skeletons of the predicted and actual segments intersect. The `clDice_loss` metric can be defined as follows:

$$\text{clDice_loss} = 1 - \frac{2 \cdot |S \cap G|}{|S| + |G|} \quad (5)$$

where S is the set of skeletonized pixels of the predicted segmentation and G is the set of skeletonized pixels of the ground truth segmentation. Soft `clDice` prioritizes the central paths of tubular structures to maintain connectivity of segmented vessels, crucial for vascular segmentation tasks.

The `avg_loss` is computed as the average of these three components.

$$\text{avg_loss} = \frac{\text{BCE} + \text{Dice_loss} + \text{clDice_loss}}{3} \quad (6)$$

This approach ensures a balanced contribution from each loss function, thereby improving overall segmentation quality. The BCE loss maintains the accuracy of the pixel level, the `Dice_loss` enhances the volumetric overlap, and the `clDice_loss` preserves the vascular structure. These components collectively form an effective loss function for PAs segmentation, improving structural accuracy.

2.7. Grid aggregator

Grid aggregators are utilized after network operation to merge segmented results into a unified image. This integration combines segments to preserve the continuity of the vascular system, resulting in an accurate segmentation map that represents the intricate PAs anatomy. Grid aggregators demonstrate the network's ability to efficiently process substantial data volumes.

2.8. Post-processing

During the post-processing phase, false positives are removed by detecting and keeping only connected regions, ensuring the validity of the final results. Furthermore, the segmented data are converted back to their anisotropic resolution to align with the initial dimensions, thereby maintaining anatomical precision.

3. Experiment

This section outlines the dataset division and the training processes of YOLOv8 and SDVN for segmentation.

3.1. Dataset division

The datasets *RIDER*, *KiTS*, *Dongyang*, *Gennimatas_1*, and *Gennimatas_2* are partitioned into three segments: 80% is allocated for training purposes, 10% is used for validation, and the remaining 10% is utilized for testing. This division was selected to ensure sufficient training data while retaining representative subsets, in line with standard practices in medical image analysis [34–37]. The *RIDER*, *KiTS*, and *Dongyang* datasets are publicly accessible, while *Gennimatas_1* and *Gennimatas_2* are private.

3.2. Data preprocessing for YOLOv8

YOLOv8 is developed to recognize and distinguish PAs, with a particular emphasis on determining the bifurcation point. The training procedure encompasses following steps to precisely identify these points.

3.2.1. Intensity clipping

The intensity clipping process is applied to the 3D CT dataset. Intensity clipping limits intensity values to a specific range, removing unnecessary details and improving the visibility of PAs in the images.

3.2.2. Cumulative intensity projection

A two-dimensional cumulative intensity projection (CIP) is created. This technique maps a three-dimensional image volume onto a two-dimensional plane by combining intensity values along the anatomical axis.

Anatomically, this process involves projecting intensity values along the axis that aligns with the natural orientation of the body, which can include the coronal, sagittal, or axial planes, depending on the orientation of the imaging data. This method simplifies the visualization of complex three-dimensional structures in a two-dimensional format, preserving important intensity data for further analysis while reducing the dimensionality.

The standard equation that regulates this procedure is as follows:

$$\text{CIP}(x, y) = \sum_{z=1}^N I(x, y, z) \quad (7)$$

Where:

- $\text{CIP}(x, y)$ represents the 2D cumulative intensity projection located at the coordinates of the plane (x, y) .
- $I(x, y, z)$ indicates the intensity value at the coordinates (x, y, z) in the 3D volume.
- z denotes index along the projection axis (depth or third dimension).
- N represents the total number of slices or layers along the projection axis.

The CIP enhances the visibility of PAs blood vessels by compiling intensity values across their depth, resulting in a clearer projection.

Fig. 5. Detection of arterial bifurcations and bounding box using yolov8 on 2D Cumulative Intensity Projections derived from 3D CT scan samples.

3.2.3. Normalization

Data normalization is conducted within the range [0, 1], which helps to reduce variability and contributes to a more stable and effective training process.

The procedure utilizes the equation below:

$$I_{\text{norm}} = \frac{I - I_{\min}}{I_{\max} - I_{\min}} \quad (8)$$

where:

- I_{norm} denotes the normalized intensity value.
- I is the initial intensity value.
- I_{\min} indicates the minimal intensity value.
- I_{\max} indicates the maximum intensity value.

3.2.4. Keypoint and bounding box annotation

In each sample, expert radiologists annotate a keypoint at the bifurcation of the PAs using Label Studio [38], where the vessel splits into two branches. These keypoints are essential for guiding the model during training. Additionally, the model uses spatial context by placing a bounding box around the bifurcation area, which is the ROI.

3.3. Training YOLOv8

The processed dataset, identical to the training set used for the SDVN model, is employed to train YOLOv8 with annotated keypoints and bounding boxes. This enables precise predictions for the specific anatomical area. This method improves the efficiency and speed of detecting arterial structures in medical imaging, particularly to identify ROI.

3.4. Training process of SDVN

After identifying ROI, the samples are used to train the SDVN network to segment PAs. This procedure involves several steps necessary for precise segmentation of the artery within the specified ROI.

3.4.1. Preprocessing

In the preprocessing stage, CT scan images are clipped on the basis of the intensity values at the 0.5 and 99.5 percentiles. This method minimizes the influence of extreme outliers (e.g. implants, ECG electrodes), thus enhancing image quality. Percentile-based clipping is

chosen instead of fixed threshold values because the dataset comprises scans from multiple centers, each with varying acquisition settings and intensity distributions. This ensures a more adaptive and consistent preprocessing across diverse data. After clipping the intensity values, the next step involves normalizing them to a standard range of [0, 1] using Eq. (8).

3.4.2. Model training

The model undergoes training for 250 epochs with a learning rate of 0.001 to identify patterns in the dataset. The training environment for SDVN comprises an AMD Ryzen Threadripper Pro 3995WX CPU, which operates at a clock speed of 2.7 GHz and possesses a 256 MB cache. The system also features 64 GB of Micron DDR4 RAM, organized into 8 x 8 GB modules operating at 3200 MHz.

4. Results and discussion

This section outlines and analyzes the performance of the proposed approach. Initially, YOLOv8 is used in test samples to detect key points that indicate ROI, specifically the arterial bifurcation point. Upon identifying these critical points, SDVN is employed to segment the arteries based on the specified locations.

4.1. YOLOv8 in identifying arterial branch locations

The trained YOLOv8 model was tested on a multicenter dataset with various artery shapes and varying intensity distributions, ensuring robustness in anatomical and imaging variations. The model accurately identified bifurcation points that aligned with the intended anatomical structures. Fig. 5 demonstrates the application of YOLOv8 to detect bifurcation points in 2D Cumulative Intensity Projections (CIP) derived from 3D CT scan samples. The bounding boxes highlight the localized ROI, and the model shows strong performance in identifying bifurcations across varying arterial geometries.

4.2. Evaluation of YOLOv8 across multiple datasets

YOLOv8 was evaluated on five diverse datasets—Dongyang Hospital, RIDER Lung CT, KiTS19, Gennimatas_1, and Gennimatas_2 to assess its effectiveness in detecting bifurcation points. The model consistently achieved high performance across key metrics, including mean Average

Fig. 6. PAs segmentation results illustrate the 3D CT scan with overlaid ground truth (green) and predicted segmentation (red). The model accurately captures arteries of varying diameters and maintains continuity across the entire vascular structure, enabling detailed comparison between predicted and true anatomical boundaries.

Table 2

Performance Metrics of YOLOv8 for Bifurcation Point Detection Across Five Diverse CT Datasets. The model demonstrates high accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-scores, indicating strong generalization across varying anatomical structures and imaging conditions.

Dataset	mAP	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Dongyang	0.99	0.99	1.00	0.99
RIDER	0.99	0.98	1.00	0.99
KiTS	0.99	1.00	1.00	0.98
Gennimatas_1	0.99	0.98	1.00	0.99
Gennimatas_2	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.99

Precision (mAP) [28], Precision, Recall, and F1-score, as detailed in Table 2. These results underscore YOLOv8's robust performance across multiple centers with varying characteristics.

4.3. Evaluation of segmentation algorithm

After detecting ROI, the PAs is segmented to highlight important anatomical characteristics. The segmented results are then evaluated using the Dice similarity coefficient (DSC), the 95th percentile of the Hausdorff distance (HD95), and the Hausdorff distance (HD) [39].

4.3.1. Loss function comparison

The contribution of individual loss functions was evaluated by training the segmentation model separately with Dice, BCE, and soft cDice losses. This analysis highlights the strengths and limitations of each formulation in capturing the complex vascular structure of PAs. As shown in Table 3, Dice loss achieves high overlap accuracy and effectively captures the overall vessel shape but may underperform at bifurcations or fine branches. BCE loss delivers comparable overlap performance while being better suited to recovering weak or thin vessel segments. Although soft cDice loss yields lower Dice scores and higher Hausdorff distances, it excels at preserving the continuity of elongated and branching structures, which makes it particularly beneficial for vascular segmentation. These results highlight the complementary properties of the loss functions used in combined training.

4.3.2. Quantitative analysis

The quantitative results are described in Table 4, which summarizes the key metrics used to evaluate the performance of the proposed

methodology. The average DSC of the test set indicates strong correspondence with the ground truth. Furthermore, the efficacy of the segmentation model is further demonstrated by the calculated values for HD and HD95.

To further assess segmentation performance across vessels of varying diameters, stratified evaluation was conducted based on artery diameter. The vessels were categorized into five diameter ranges: 3 to 6 mm, 7 to 9 mm, 10 to 12 mm, 13 to 15 mm, and 16 to 18 mm. As shown in Table 5, the model maintained a consistently high Dice coefficient in all groups, with a Dice score of 0.87 even in the smallest diameter range (3 to 6 mm), which is particularly relevant for the distal arteries. Performance improved with increasing vessel diameter, reaching a Dice of 0.95 in the 15–18 mm range. Similar trends were observed in Hausdorff distance (HD) and HD95 metrics, where smaller vessels showed higher values due to increased sensitivity to boundary variations. These results demonstrate the robustness of the proposed method in accurately segmenting small and large vessels, supporting its suitability for clinical use in the evaluation of PAD.

4.3.3. Visual evaluation

The model segments PAs in a range of vessel diameters, accurately delineating both large proximal segments and thin distal branches. This segmentation maintains connectivity throughout the arterial network, producing a continuous mask that follows each vessel without fragmentation or gaps. The predicted segmentation closely matches the annotated ground truth, as evidenced by the substantial overlap when the ground truth (green) and predicted (red) contours are overlaid in Fig. 6. The substantial overlap between the predicted and annotated contours reflects the effectiveness of the model in delineating the morphology of the PAs.

Table 3
Average performance metrics for Dice, BCE, and cLDice loss functions.

Loss Type	Dice Score	HD (mm)	HD95 (mm)
Dice Loss	0.86	42.71	5.38
BCE Loss	0.85	38.11	6.32
Soft CLDice Loss	0.62	82.50	22.95

Table 4
Comparison of U-Net, ResUNet, DenseNet, SAMMed-3D, TotalSegmentator, and Proposed Method on PAs Segmentation Across Five Datasets.

Dataset	Metric	3D U-Net	ResUNet	DenseNet	SAM-Med3D	TotalSegmentator	Proposed
Dongyang	Dice	0.70	0.77	0.85	0.79	0.78	0.90
	HD (mm)	32.4	36.27	13.95	12.75	14.57	3.03
	HD95 (mm)	13.8	20.73	1.20	2.28	3.83	1.00
RIDER	Dice	0.60	0.78	0.83	0.68	0.69	0.90
	HD (mm)	65.74	31.14	99.34	105.76	106.74	26.41
	HD95 (mm)	12.20	2.44	12.44	21.54	65.50	1.40
KiTS	Dice	0.72	0.82	0.82	0.76	0.75	0.91
	HD (mm)	47.84	43.18	59.04	24.01	43.53	11.74
	HD95 (mm)	13.86	11.28	17.95	3.46	15.02	1.21
Gennimatas_1	Dice	0.67	0.72	0.83	0.67	0.58	0.90
	HD (mm)	45.44	53.44	32.66	53.48	100.00	14.28
	HD95 (mm)	12.4	29.80	1.50	3.00	79.91	1.00
Gennimatas_2	Dice	0.85	0.88	0.88	0.81	0.76	0.92
	HD (mm)	27.23	37.41	39.6	48.25	54.27	7.54
	HD95 (mm)	1.50	5.59	3.39	4.09	30.51	1.00

Table 5
Segmentation performance across different artery diameter ranges.

Diameter Range (mm)	Dice	HD (mm)	HD95 (mm)
3–6	0.87	9.01	3.30
7–9	0.91	9.47	1.06
10–12	0.91	6.43	1.10
13–15	0.91	4.53	1.31
16–18	0.95	2.14	0.75

4.4. Comparison with existing methods

In recent years, medical image segmentation has seen substantial progress; however, there is still a lack of algorithms tailored specifically for PAs segmentation. Table 4 presents a comprehensive comparison of PAs segmentation performance in five data sets using six methods. U-Net [40], ResUNet [41], DenseNet [42], SAM-Med3D [43], TotalSegmentator [44], and the proposed approach. Fig. 7 provides a visual comparison of the PA segmentation results of six methods: 3D U-Net, Residual U-Net, DenseNet, TotalSegmentator, SAM-Med3D and the proposed approach. The proposed method demonstrates superior vessel boundary delineation and improved continuity across slices, especially in challenging regions with low contrast, irregular vessel, and small vessel diameters.

In the Dongyang dataset, proposed method achieves a Dice of 0.90, with a notably low HD of 3.03 mm and HD95 of 1.00 mm, indicating high segmentation accuracy and boundary precision. In the RIDER dataset, the presence of an extended internal iliac artery increases HD. However, our method achieves a substantially lower HD of 26.41 mm, compared to much higher values reported by other approaches, such as 99.34 mm by DenseNet and 106.74 mm by TotalSegmentator. In the KiTS dataset, the proposed method achieves the highest Dice score of 0.91, along with substantial reductions in HD and HD95, mitigating boundary discrepancies common in conventional networks. Performance gains are especially notable in the Gennimatas datasets, where Dice scores of 0.90 and 0.92 are achieved with consistently low HD and HD95 values, despite contrast variability. These results collectively highlight the robustness, generalizability, and boundary precision of the proposed segmentation framework, supporting its clinical utility in PAs analysis.

Among the publicly available segmentation tools trained in diverse large-scale medical imaging datasets, SAM-Med3D and TotalSegmentator have emerged as two of the most widely adopted for the delineation

of anatomical structures. SAM-Med is recognized for its strong performance in segmenting medical structures using the Segment Anything Model (SAM) within medical imaging contexts. Adapted to the anatomical variability and imaging characteristics of CT scans, it benefits from training on a wide range of annotated medical datasets. However, SAM-Med requires manual interaction in the form of point selection to initiate the segmentation process, which limits its applicability in fully automated clinical workflows. This reliance on user input makes it less practical for large-scale or time-sensitive applications where automation and consistency are critical. In terms of performance, SAM-Med achieved moderate results with Dice scores ranging from 0.67 to 0.81, it was unable to accurately follow the course of the internal iliac artery, leading to inconsistent segmentation in complex vascular regions.

Furthermore, TotalSegmentator is well-known for effectively segmenting over 100 anatomical structures in CT and MRI images, supporting 117 CT classes and 56 MRI classes. It is trained on a diverse dataset from various scanners and institutions, built on the nnU-Net [45] framework. The proposed method and TotalSegmentator are compared using DSC, HD, and HD95, as shown in Table 4. The proposed method achieved mean values of 0.91 for DSC, 12.60 mm for HD, and 1.12 mm for HD95, whereas TotalSegmentator recorded mean values of 0.71 for DSC, 63.82 mm for HD, and 38.95 mm for HD95. The proposed method is accurate and reliable in detecting the PA system in CT data, allowing detailed tracking of vascular structures, crucial for surgical planning, disease monitoring, and interventions. In contrast, TotalSegmentator exhibits significant limitations in both scope and consistency. Its segmentation is largely limited to the common iliac artery, with reduced performance in detecting distal or smaller vascular structures.

The common iliac artery, originating from the bifurcation of the abdominal aorta, is a critical vessel that supplies oxygenated blood to the pelvis and lower limbs. Subsequently, it divides into the internal iliac

Fig. 7. Visual comparison of PAs segmentation results obtained using 3D U-Net, Residual U-Net, DenseNet, TotalSegmentator, MedSAM3D, and the proposed methodology. The proposed method shows improved vessel boundary delineation and better continuity across slices, particularly in challenging regions with low contrast and small vessel diameters.

Fig. 8. Comparison between the proposed methodology and an existing segmentation approach (TotalSegmentator). While TotalSegmentator is limited to segmenting only the common iliac artery, the proposed method demonstrates the ability to segment the entire PAs system.

Table 6
Comparison of Proposed Methodology and Total Segmentator for Common Iliac Artery Segmentation Across Five Centers.

Centers	Proposed : DSC	TotalSegmentator: DSC	Proposed : HD (mm)	TotalSegmentator: HD (mm)	Proposed : HD95 (mm)	TotalSegmentator: HD95 (mm)
Dongyang	0.91	0.80	2.45	5.42	1.00	1.71
RIDER	0.93	0.82	7.34	16.54	1.00	2.24
KiTS	0.92	0.83	5.80	8.91	1.21	2.29
Gennimatas_set1	0.93	0.86	3.23	6.52	1.00	1.0
Gennimatas_set2	0.93	0.87	5.03	7.74	1.21	1.0

artery, which supplies the pelvic organs, and the external iliac artery, which continues towards the lower extremities. TotalSegmentator fails to provide a complete representation of the PA system, making it less suitable for comprehensive vascular analysis.

Fig. 8 presents a comparison between the proposed methodology and the existing segmentation tool, TotalSegmentator. TotalSegmentator segments the common iliac artery but is limited to this proximal region, not capturing the entire PAs. In contrast, the proposed method

is designed to segment the entire PAs network, which includes both the common iliac artery and its distal branches. The ability of the proposed method to segment the entire arterial tree improves diagnostic insight and supports more effective surgical planning, especially in complex vascular cases where distal artery involvement is critical.

Additionally, Table 6 provides a quantitative comparison of the proposed methodology and TotalSegmentator for segmenting only the common iliac artery across five centers. The proposed method achieved a Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) of 0.92, a Hausdorff Distance (HD) of 4.77 mm, and a HD95 of 1.08 mm. In contrast, TotalSegmentator obtained a DSC of 0.836, an HD of 8.92 mm, and a HD95 of 1.85 mm. These results highlight the improved accuracy and consistency of the proposed approach.

4.5. Limitations and future work

Despite the promising results, some limitations remain. In particular, the model was not trained on cases involving highly tortuous or occluded arteries. The absence of fully or partially occluded arteries in the training data further restricts the model's ability to accurately detect or segment vessels affected by severe stenosis or blockage. These gaps limit the applicability of the method for patients with advanced vascular disease. To address this, future work will explore transfer learning to improve model generalization, particularly for cases with limited annotated data or complex pathological variations [46,47]. Using pre-trained models and fine-tuning them in domain-specific data sets, the robustness and applicability of the method in various vascular anatomies are expected to improve.

In addition, efforts will focus on ensuring that the segmentation output is compatible with widely used hemodynamic simulation platforms such as ANSYS and SimVascular. This integration will facilitate the application of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analyses, which are increasingly used in clinical settings for the evaluation and treatment planning of vascular diseases.

5. Conclusion

Segmentation of PAs is a challenging task due to factors such as variable vessel diameters, low image resolutions, and significant anatomical differences, which traditional techniques often struggle to resolve. The suggested method addresses these issues by using diverse datasets, thereby improving segmentation reliability in a range of imaging circumstances. A key advancement of this method is the integration of an improved YOLOv8 model to precisely detect ROI before segmentation, reducing computational complexity and increasing segmentation accuracy. Additionally, the SDVN network, single encoder–decoder architecture preserves high-resolution features, enabling segmentation of both large and small vessels, including those crucial for the early diagnosis of PAs disease. Pre-processing techniques improve image quality, while post-processing refinements eliminate false positives and maintain vessel continuity. These improvements contribute to more precise and reliable segmentations, which are essential for clinical decision-making in vascular assessment. Future work will focus on further improving performance by incorporating adaptive learning strategies and multimodal imaging data to improve segmentation across diverse clinical settings.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Manahil Zulfiqar: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Maciej Stanuch:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Sylvia Vagena:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Data curation. **Fragiska Sigala:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Data curation. **Andrzej Skalski:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Ethics statement

KiTS, Dongyang and RIDER datasets are publicly available under license CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 and the End User License Agreement (EULA). Furthermore, Ethical approval has been granted for the use of this dataset in the study (approvals 9876/28.3.24 and 11293/9.4.24) for Gennimatas_1 and Gennimatas_2.

Code availability

A public GitHub repository has been created to ensure reproducibility. The repository contains all the necessary scripts. <https://github.com/manahilzz/Automated-Segmentation-of-Peripheral-Arteries-in-3D-CT-data-based-on-a-Single-Depth-Vascular-Network>.

AI statement

During the preparation of this work the authors used Wirtefull in order to improve language clarity. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be available on reasonable request and the code is available at <https://github.com/manahilzz/Automated-Segmentation-of-Peripheral-Arteries-in-3D-CT-data-based-on-a-Single-Depth-Vascular-Network>.

References

- [1] M.H. Criqui, K. Matsushita, V. Aboyans, C.N. Hess, C.W. Hicks, T.W. Kwan, M.M. McDermott, S. Misra, F. Ujueta, Lower extremity peripheral artery disease: Contemporary epidemiology, management gaps, and future directions: A scientific statement from the American heart association, *Circulation* 144 (9) (2021) e171–e191, URL <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/10.1161/CIR.0000000000001005>.
- [2] T.S. Polonsky, M.M. McDermott, Lower extremity peripheral artery disease without chronic limb-threatening ischemia: a review, *Jama* 325 (21) (2021) 2188–2198.
- [3] G. Agnelli, J.J. Belch, I. Baumgartner, P. Giovias, U. Hoffmann, Morbidity and mortality associated with atherosclerotic peripheral artery disease: A systematic review, *Atherosclerosis* 293 (2019) 94–100, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2019.09.012>.
- [4] J. Nordanstig, C. Behrendt, A. Bradbury, G. de Borst, F. Fowkes, J. Golledge, A. Gottsater, R. Hinchliffe, S. Nikol, L. Norgren, Peripheral arterial disease (PAD)—A challenging manifestation of atherosclerosis, *Prev. Med.* 171 (2023) 107489.
- [5] E.M. Nasab, S.S. Athari, The prevalence of thoracic aorta aneurysm as an important cardiovascular disease in the general population, *J. Cardiothorac. Surg.* 17 (1) (2022) 67, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13019-022-01767-0>, URL <https://cardiothoracicsurgery.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13019-022-01767-0>.
- [6] V. Aboyans, J.-B. Ricco, M.-L. Bartelink, M. Björck, M. Brodmann, T. Cohner, J.-P. Collet, M. Czerny, M. De Carlo, S. Debus, 2017 ESC guidelines on the diagnosis and treatment of peripheral arterial diseases, in collaboration with the European Society for Vascular Surgery (ESVS), *Kardiol. Polska (Pol. Hear. J.)* 75 (11) (2017) 1065–1160.
- [7] L. Norgren, et al., Inter-society consensus for the management of peripheral arterial disease (TASC II), *J. Vasc. Surg.* 45 (1) (2007) S5–S67.
- [8] B. Tran, Assessment and management of peripheral arterial disease: what every cardiologist should know, *Heart* 107 (22) (2019) 1835–1842.

- [9] O. Shwaiki, B. Rashwan, M.A. Fink, L. Kirksey, S. Gadani, K. Karuppusamy, C. Melzig, D. Thompson, G. D'Amico, F. Rengier, et al., Lower extremity CT angiography in peripheral arterial disease: from the established approach to evolving technical developments, *Int. J. Cardiovasc. Imaging* 37 (2021) 3101–3114.
- [10] D. Fleischmann, R.L. Hallett, G.D. Rubin, CT angiography of peripheral arterial disease, *J. Vasc. Interv. Radiol.* 17 (1) (2006) 3–26.
- [11] X. Li, L. Zhang, J. Yang, F. Teng, Role of artificial intelligence in medical image analysis: A review of current trends and future directions, *J. Med. Biol. Eng.* (2024) 1–13.
- [12] V. Aboyans, J.-B. Ricco, M.-L.E.L. Bartelink, et al., 2017 ESC guidelines on the diagnosis and treatment of peripheral arterial diseases, *Eur. Heart J.* 39 (9) (2017) 763–816.
- [13] J. Springer, et al., *A State-Of-The-Art Review on Coronary Artery Border Segmentation*, Springer, 2023.
- [14] P. Abdulhannan, D. Russell, S. Homer-Vanniasinkam, Peripheral arterial disease: a literature review, *Br. Med. Bull.* 104 (1) (2012) 21–39.
- [15] A.M. Flores, F. Demas, N.J. Leeper, E.G. Ross, Leveraging machine learning and artificial intelligence to improve peripheral artery disease detection, treatment, and outcomes, *Circ. Res.* 128 (12) (2021) 1833–1850.
- [16] A.F. Dima, V.A. Zimmer, M.J. Menten, H.B. Li, M. Graf, T. Lemke, D. Rueckert, 3D arterial segmentation via single 2D projections and depth supervision in contrast-enhanced CT images, in: *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention*, Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2023, pp. 141–151.
- [17] Z. Guo, Z. Tan, J. Feng, J. Zhou, 3D vascular segmentation supervised by 2D annotation of maximum intensity projection, *IEEE Trans. Med. Imaging* (2024).
- [18] H. Chen, X. Wang, H. Li, L. Wang, 3D vessel segmentation with limited guidance of 2D structure-agnostic vessel annotations, *IEEE J. Biomed. Heal. Inform.* (2024).
- [19] G. Hu, Y. Chen, C. Mu, X. Zhang, Y. Wang, Y. Wang, Z. Jin, Association of lower extremity peripheral arterial disease with quantitative muscle features from computed tomography angiography, *Insights Into Imaging* 15 (1) (2024) 95.
- [20] J.J. Westenberg, R.J. van der Geest, M.N. Wasser, E.L. van der Linden, T. van Walsum, H.C. van Assen, J.H. Reiber, Vessel diameter measurements in gadolinium contrast-enhanced three-dimensional MRA of peripheral arteries, *Magn. Reson. Imaging* 18 (1) (2000) 13–22.
- [21] J. Wu, J. Smith, Transformer-based 3D U-Net for vascular structure segmentation, *Med. Imaging J.* 45 (3) (2023) 123–134.
- [22] M. Mirzafam, N. Aghazadeh, A three-stage shearlet-based algorithm for vessel segmentation in medical imaging, *Pattern Anal. Appl.* 24 (2) (2021) 591–610.
- [23] M.E. Rayed, S.S. Islam, S.I. Niha, J.R. Jim, M.M. Kabir, M. Mridha, Deep learning for medical image segmentation: State-of-the-art advancements and challenges, *Informatics Med. Unlocked* (2024) 101504.
- [24] A.F. AbuRahma, J.E. Campbell, Overview of peripheral arterial disease of the lower extremity, in: *Noninvasive Vascular Diagnosis: A Practical Textbook for Clinicians*, Springer, 2022, pp. 449–488.
- [25] L. Radl, Y. Jin, A. Pepe, J. Li, C. Gsaxner, F. hua Zhao, J. Egger, AVT: Multicenter aortic vessel tree CTA dataset collection with ground truth segmentation masks, *Data Brief* 40 (2022) 107801, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2022.107801>, URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352340922000130>.
- [26] Z. Yaniv, B.C. Lowekamp, H.J. Johnson, R. Beare, SimpleITK image-analysis notebooks: a collaborative environment for education and reproducible research, *J. Digit. Imaging* 31 (3) (2018) 290–303.
- [27] Ultralytics, Ultralytics YOLOv11, 2024, URL <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>.
- [28] N. Jegham, C.Y. Koh, M. Abdelatti, A. Hendawi, Evaluating the evolution of yolo (you only look once) models: A comprehensive benchmark study of yolo11 and its predecessors, 2024, arXiv preprint arXiv:2411.00201.
- [29] N. Cordier, B. Menze, H. Delingette, N. Ayache, Patch-based segmentation of brain tissues, in: *MICCAI Challenge on Multimodal Brain Tumor Segmentation*, IEEE, 2013, pp. 6–17.
- [30] S. Rajaraman, G. Zamzmi, S.K. Antani, Novel loss functions for ensemble-based medical image classification, *PloS One* 16 (12) (2021) e0261307.
- [31] G. Litjens, T. Kooi, B.E. Bejnordi, A.A.A. Setio, F. Ciompi, M. Ghafoorian, J.A. Van Der Laak, B. Van Ginneken, C.I. Sánchez, A survey on deep learning in medical image analysis, *Med. Image Anal.* 42 (2017) 60–88.
- [32] F. Milletari, N. Navab, S.-A. Ahmadi, V-Net: Fully convolutional neural networks for volumetric medical image segmentation, in: *2016 Fourth International Conference on 3D Vision (3DV)*, 2016, pp. 565–571, URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7785132>.
- [33] S. Shit, J.C. Paetzold, A. Sekuboyina, I. Ezhov, A. Unger, A. Zhylyka, J.P. Plum, U. Bauer, B.H. Menze, Cldice-a novel topology-preserving loss function for tubular structure segmentation, in: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2021, pp. 16560–16569.
- [34] P. Bhardwaj, S. Bhat, A. Maier, Enhancing zero-shot learning in medical imaging: integrating clip with advanced techniques for improved chest x-ray analysis, 2025, arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.13134.
- [35] C. Lokker, E. Bagheri, W. Abdelkader, R. Parrish, M. Afzal, T. Navarro, C. Cotoi, F. Germini, L. Linkins, R.B. Haynes, et al., Deep learning to refine the identification of high-quality clinical research articles from the biomedical literature: performance evaluation, *J. Biomed. Inform.* 142 (2023) 104384.
- [36] L. Faes, S.K. Wagner, D.J. Fu, X. Liu, E. Korot, J.R. LedSAM, T. Back, R. Chopra, N. Pontikos, C. Kern, et al., Automated deep learning design for medical image classification by health-care professionals with no coding experience: a feasibility study, *Lancet Digit. Heal.* 1 (5) (2019) e232–e242.
- [37] P. Dermyer, A. Kalra, M. Schwartz, EndoDINO: A foundation model for GI endoscopy, 2025, arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.05488.
- [38] M. Tkachenko, M. Malyuk, A. Holmanyuk, N. Liubimov, Label Studio: Data labeling software, 2020–2025, URL <https://github.com/HumanSignal/label-studio>, Open source software available from <https://github.com/HumanSignal/label-studio>.
- [39] *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, A fully automated method for segmenting arteries and veins in MRA images, *Front. Neurosci.* 14 (2020) 537.
- [40] V.W.H. Wong, M. Ferguson, K.H. Law, Y.-T.T. Lee, P. Witherell, Automatic volumetric segmentation of additive manufacturing defects with 3D U-net, 2021, arXiv preprint arXiv:2101.08993.
- [41] H. Ko, J. Huh, K.W. Kim, H. Chung, Y. Ko, J.K. Kim, J.H. Lee, J. Lee, A deep residual U-Net algorithm for automatic detection and quantification of ascites on abdominopelvic computed tomography images acquired in the emergency department: model development and validation, *J. Med. Internet Res.* 24 (1) (2022) e34415.
- [42] L.-S. Pan, C.-W. Li, S.-F. Su, S.-Y. Tay, Q.-V. Tran, W.P. Chan, Coronary artery segmentation under class imbalance using a U-Net based architecture on computed tomography angiography images, *Sci. Rep.* 11 (1) (2021) 14493.
- [43] H. Wang, S. Guo, J. Ye, Z. Deng, J. Cheng, T. Li, J. Chen, Y. Su, Z. Huang, Y. Shen, et al., Sam-med3d: towards general-purpose segmentation models for volumetric medical images, in: *European Conference on Computer Vision*, Springer, 2025, pp. 51–67.
- [44] J. Wasserthal, M. Meyer, H. Breit, J. Cyriac, S. Yang, M. Segeroth, TotalSegmentator: Robust segmentation of 104 anatomical structures in CT images, *Radiol. Artif. Intell.* 4 (6) (2022) e220193.
- [45] F. Isensee, J. Petersen, A. Klein, D. Zimmerer, P.F. Jaeger, S. Kohl, J. Wasserthal, G. Koehler, T. Norajitra, S. Wirkert, K.H. Maier-Hein, nnU-Net: Self-adapting framework for U-Net-based medical image segmentation, 2018, arXiv preprint arXiv:1809.10486.
- [46] S.-Y. Lu, Y.-D. Zhang, Y.-D. Yao, An efficient vision transformer for Alzheimer's disease classification using magnetic resonance images, *Biomed. Signal Process. Control.* 101 (2025) 107263.
- [47] S.-Y. Lu, Z. Zhu, Y. Tang, X. Zhang, X. Liu, CTBViT: A novel ViT for tuberculosis classification with efficient block and randomized classifier, *Biomed. Signal Process. Control.* 100 (2025) 106981.